

Terpenoids and Related Compounds : Part 29¹. Molecular Rearrangements of Glut-5 α , 6 α -epoxy-3 β -yl Acetate

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Molecular rearrangements of glut-5 α , 6 α -epoxy-3 β -yl acetate (1) were studied with aqueous perchloric acid and with borontrifluoride etherate in benzene. While the former reagent furnished the diene (3) and the enediol (4a), the latter reagent yielded the diene (13) and the enediol monoacetate (14a).

IN a general programme for the study of molecular rearrangements of friedooleanane derivatives¹⁻⁶, we have undertaken a study on the action of aqueous perchloric acid and of borontrifluoride etherate on glut-5 α , 6 α -epoxy-3 β -yl acetate (1), prepared by epoxidation of glut-5-en-3 β -yl acetate (2) with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid.

The mass spectra of the epoxide (1) revealed fragmentation patterns in agreement with those of similar class of triterpenoids⁷⁻⁹. The α -orientation of the epoxide oxygen was favoured from steric considerations and also from nmr spectra. The proton at C-6 appeared as a quartet (1H) around δ 3.1 ppm (J_{ee} = 3Hz and J_{ae} = 4Hz).

was shown to be glut-5, 12-dien-3 β -yl acetate (3) from uv, ir, nmr and mass spectral data (see Experimental). The next polar product (ca 60%) was the unchanged epoxide (1). The most polar product (ca 10%) was shown to be a new diol (4a), which furnished a diacetate (4b). The structures of (4a) and (4b) were established from uv, ir, nmr and mass spectral data (see Experimental). The suggested mechanistic interpretation for the formation of (3) involving nucleophilic attack by water on the protonated epoxide (5) is shown in Scheme 1.

The departure of H₂O and the backbone rearrangement from the cation (6) was not a synchronous process because of the unfavourable configuration of the substitution at C-5. It may be visualised that the classical cation (7) was first formed which triggered the subsequent backbone rearrangement and final elimination of H₂O to produce the diene (3). A similar situation was encountered by Torii *et al*¹⁰ in the rearrangement of D : A-friedooleana-3 β , 4 β -epoxide (8) to dendropanoxide (9).

Treatment of the epoxide (1) with aqueous perchloric acid in tetrahydrofuran for 10 hr at room temperature gave two isolable products besides the unchanged starting material. The least polar product (ca 20%) was a nonconjugated diene, which

The formation of the diol (4a) in very small amount (ca 10%) could be explained in the following manner. The acetoxy group (or the hydroxyl group formed in small amount in presence of aqueous perchloric acid) at C-3 was β -axial and so could lead to the olefinic epoxide (10) in presence of acid. The subsequent steps are shown in Scheme 2.

A similar migration of 4β -methyl group to 5β position had been reported earlier by Halsall *et al*¹¹ when the epoxide (II) was converted to the hydroxy ketone (12) on treatment with BF_3 -ether complex.

Finally the epoxide (1) on treatment with BF_3 -etherate in anhydrous benzene for 30 min at room

temperature furnished a mixture which could be resolved by chromatography into two components. The less polar one (ca 30-40% yield) was identified as the previously known glut-1 (10), 5-dien- 3β -yl acetate (13)¹² while the more polar component was shown to be glut-5 (10)-en- 3β -acetoxy- 6α -ol (14a). The latter was converted into the diacetate (14b), whose structure was established on the basis of uv, ir, nmr and mass spectral data (see Experimental). In a nonpolar solvent like benzene the epoxide (1) formed the ion-pair (15) in a cage of solvent when treated with BF_3 -ether complex. The subsequent steps leading to (13) and (14a) are shown in Scheme 3.

Experimental

All m. ps were uncorrected. Pet ether used had b.p. $60-80^\circ$. The optical rotations were taken in chloroform solution.

Epoxidation of Glut-5-en- 3β -yl acetate (2) :

m-Chloroperbenzoic acid (2.5 g) in chloroform (50 ml) was added with stirring to a solution of glut-5-en- 3β -yl acetate (2, 2 g) in chloroform (50 ml) kept at 0° . The reaction was followed by t.l.c. on silica gel and was complete within 8 hr. Usual work up yielded a crystalline residue which on crystallisation from chloroform-acetone gave glut-5 α , 6α -epoxy- 3β -yl acetate (1), m.p. $216-218^\circ \text{C}$; $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +47.6^\circ$ (Found : C, 79.55 ; H, 10.48. $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_8$ requires : C, 79.28 ; H, 10.81%) ; $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{solid}}$ 1730, 1260 (acetate), 1380, 1360 (gem dimethyl), 892, 800 (epoxy ring) cm^{-1} ; (nmr has been discussed earlier) ; m/e 484 (M^+ , 100%), 424 ($[\text{M}-\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}]^+$, 24.38%), 469 ($[\text{M}-\text{CH}_3]^+$, 47.17%), 205 (54.04%), 135 (18.84%) and 119 (23.10%).

Reaction of the Epoxide (1) with Aqueous Perchloric Acid :

A suspension of the epoxide (1, 1.5 g) in tetrahydrofuran (60 ml) was treated dropwise with perchloric acid (3N, 11 ml) and the mixture was stirred for 10 hr at room temperature. Then 5% sodium hydrogen carbonate solution was added and the product was extracted with ether. The residue (1.5 g) from the ether extract on chromatography over a column of silica gel (100 g) furnished three

components. The first component from benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 9) was *gluta-5, 12-dien-3 β -yl acetate* (3, 0.25 g), m.p. 208-210° (chloroform-methanol); $[\alpha]_D = +11.8^\circ$ (Found : C, 82.28; H, 10.85. C₂₂H₃₀O₂ requires : C, 82.34; H, 10.80%); $\nu_{\max}^{\text{nujol}}$ 1730, 1255 (acetate), 1380, 1360 (gem-dimethyl) and 840 (trisubstituted double bond) cm⁻¹. ¹H nmr, δ (CDCl₃) 1.95 (3H, S, OCOCH₃), 5.1 br (1H, 6-H), 5.55 br (1H, 12-H), 4.6 [1H, q, J = 10 Hz ($\phi_{aa} \cong 180^\circ$)] and J = 6 Hz ($\phi_{ae} \cong 60^\circ$), 3-H], 0.8-1.05 (eight tertiary methyls); m/e 466 (M⁺), 406 ([M - CH₃COOH]⁺, 100%), 391 ([M - {CH₃COOH + CH₃}]⁺, 12.84%), 259 (57.90%), 132 (46.03%), 205 (36.23%) and 171 (30.43%).

The second component (0.9 g) eluted from the column with benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 4) had m.p. 212-215° (chloroform-acetone) and was identical in all respects with the starting epoxide (1) (ir, Co-TLC, mixed m.p.).

The most polar component eluted with benzene-ethyl acetate (9 : 1), corresponded to *friedel-3-en-2 β , 6 β -diol* (4a, 0.25 g). Recrystallisation from chloroform-methanol gave the pure diol (4a), m.p. 280-285°; $[\alpha]_D = +8^\circ$, $\nu_{\max}^{\text{nujol}}$ 3340 br (OH), 1375, 1360 (gem-dimethyl) and 840 cm⁻¹ (trisubstituted double bond). ¹H nmr, δ (CDCl₃) 5.5 (1H, ill-defined multiplet, 3-H), 3.25 br (2H, 2 × OH, disappeared on D₂O exchange), 3.45 (1H, m, 6-H), 4.25 (1H, m, allylic proton on C-2), 1.0-1.3 (seven tertiary methyls); m/e 442 (M⁺), 424 ([M - H₂O]⁺, 100%), 406 ([M - {H₂O + H₂O}]⁺, 12.37%), 391 ([M - {2H₂O + CH₃}]⁺, 14.34%), 205 (44.08%) and 135 (38.33%).

The diol (4a, 0.1 g) was acetylated as usual with Ac₂O (1 ml) and pyridine (1 ml) and the product on crystallisation from chloroform-methanol yielded *friedel-2 β , 6 β -diacetox-3-ene* (4b), m.p. 262-268° (Found : C, 77.43; H, 10.29. C₂₄H₃₄O₄ requires : C, 77.52; H, 10.33%); $\nu_{\max}^{\text{nujol}}$ 1735, 1245 (acetate), 1375, 1360 (gem-dimethyl) and 840 (trisubstituted double bond) cm⁻¹. ¹H nmr, δ (CDCl₃) 1.9 and 1.95 (6H, S, 2 × OCOCH₃), 5.3 (2H, m, methine proton on C-2 + olefinic proton on C-3; the chemical shift of the methine proton on C-2 is expected to fall in the olefinic region¹⁸), 4.6 [1H, q, J = 11 Hz ($\phi_{aa} \cong 180^\circ$)] and J = 7 Hz ($\phi_{ae} \cong 60^\circ$), 6-H], 0.75-1.3 (seven tertiary methyls). The methyl group attached to the olefinic bond at C-4 appeared slightly in the downfield region δ 1.5 ppm due to the deshielding effect of the double bond.

Reaction of the Epoxide(I) with Borontrifluoride Etherate :

A solution of the epoxide (1, 1 g) in dry benzene (50 ml) was treated with freshly distilled borontrifluoride etherate (1 ml) and the mixture was stirred

for 30 min at room temperature, when the mixture became pale yellow. Usual work up furnished a gummy mass (1.2 g) which was chromatographed over a column of silica gel (100 g). Benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 9) eluted *gluta-1(10), 5-dien-3 β -yl acetate* (13, 0.35 g), m.p. 210-215° (chloroform-acetone) (lit.¹², 208-210°); $[\alpha]_D = +37.7^\circ$ (Found : C, 82.09; H, 10.73. calc. for C₂₂H₃₀O₂ : C, 82.34; H, 10.80%); $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}}(\epsilon)$ 232 (16 500), 238 (18 000) and

246 nm (inflection) (11 000); $\nu_{\max}^{\text{nujol}}$ 1730, 1245 (acetate), 1380, 1365 (gem-dimethyl) and 860 (trisubstituted double bond) cm⁻¹. ¹H nmr, δ (CDCl₃) 1.95 (3H, S, OCOCH₃), 5.1 br (1H, 6-H), 5.55 br (1H, 1-H), 4.6 [1H, q, J = 10 Hz ($\phi_{aa} \cong 180^\circ$)] and J = 6 Hz ($\phi_{ae} \cong 60^\circ$), 3-H], 0.8-1.05 (eight tertiary methyls); m/e 466 (M⁺), 406 ([M - CH₃COOH]⁺, 100%), 391 ([M - {CH₃COOH + CH₃}]⁺, 27.46%), 253 (3.79%), 171 (39.22%) and 205 (58.05%).

Subsequent elution of the column with benzene yielded *glut-5(10)-en-3 β -acetox-6 α -ol* (14a) (0.6 g), m.p. 232-235° (chloroform-methanol); $[\alpha]_D = +129.6^\circ$; $\nu_{\max}^{\text{nujol}}$ 3400 br (OH), 1740 and 1245 (acetate) cm⁻¹. The hydroxy compound (14a) was acetylated with a mixture of acetic anhydride and pyridine in the usual manner to furnish the diacetate (14b), m.p. 155-160° (chloroform-methanol); $[\alpha]_D = +158.3^\circ$ (Found : C, 77.08; H, 10.49. C₂₄H₃₄O₄ requires : C, 77.52; H, 10.33%); $\nu_{\max}^{\text{nujol}}$ 1735, 1250 (acetate), 1380 and 1365 (gem-dimethyl) cm⁻¹. ¹H nmr, δ (CDCl₃) 1.9 and 2.0 (6H, S, 2 × OCOCH₃), 5.2 br (2H, m, α -H on C-3 + β -H on C-6), 0.8-1.1 (eight tertiary methyls). Absence of any olefinic proton indicated the tetrasubstituted nature of the double bond. m/e 526 (M⁺), 466 ([M - CH₃COOH]⁺, 100%), 406 ([M - {CH₃COOH + CH₃COOH}]⁺, 43.48%), 391 ([M - {2 × CH₃COOH + CH₃}]⁺, 34.45%), 205 (51.15%), 253 (4.48%), 171 (31.86) and 135 (12.86%).

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